

Curriculum shifts and their echo in Teacher Licensure Examination results

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the impact of curriculum reforms on the academic performance and Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) results of graduates in the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) and Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) programs at King's College of the Philippines–Bambang Inc. Recognizing the evolving demands of teacher preparation, the study aimed to determine whether differences between the Old and New curricula influenced graduates' academic achievement, subject-area performance in the LET, passing rates, and the relationship between overall academic performance and licensure outcomes. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed, utilizing purposive sampling to include graduates from the 2018–2019 (Old curriculum) and 2022–2023 (New curriculum) cohorts. Academic records and LET results were analyzed using descriptive statistics, t-tests, Spearman's rho, and Pearson r to identify differences and correlations. The findings revealed that graduates under both curricula demonstrated above-average academic performance, with the New curriculum showing slightly higher outcomes. In LET results, the Old curriculum graduates generally achieved higher and more consistent scores, while the New curriculum graduates showed improvement in specific subject areas but greater variability overall. No significant relationship was found between overall academic performance and LET performance for either curriculum. Passing rates varied across programs, with some notable gains under the New curriculum, highlighting that curriculum reform enhances academic preparedness and subject-specific competence but does not uniformly guarantee higher licensure success. These results suggest that continuous curriculum evaluation, targeted support in Majorship subjects, and additional preparatory strategies are essential to optimize graduates' readiness for the teaching profession. Overall, both curricula produced competent graduates, but careful refinement of the New curriculum may better align student learning outcomes with licensure requirements.

Keywords: academic performance, curriculum reform, Licensure Examination, teacher education, teaching readiness

Date Submitted: July 1, 2025

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.69651/PIJHSS0403447>

Recommended citation:

Marcelino, M. A. P. (2025). Curriculum shifts and their echo in Teacher Licensure Examination results. *Pantao (The International Journal of the Humanities and Social Sciences)* 4 (3), 4808-4819.

<http://doi.org/10.69651/PIJHSS0403447>

Date Accepted: August 2, 2025

Date Published: August 16, 2025

INTRODUCTION

The quality of education is a crucial aspect of national development, and the curriculum plays a significant role in the formation of the capabilities of future educators. In recent years, changes in the curriculum have caused discussions about their impact, particularly about teacher licensing exams. As educational systems evolve, understanding how curriculum adjustments influence the performance of potential teachers becomes essential to promote effective teaching and learning. The Philippines serves as a pertinent case study, reflecting more internationally observed trends.

In countries such as Finland, widely recognized for their high educational standards, curriculum changes have been implemented to meet evolving skill requirements. The focus on skills, instead of routine learning, influenced licensing exams, aiming at a more dynamic assessment of teachers' readiness (Banjal, Berame, and Elasio, 2025).

Similarly, internationally, several educational bodies have observed the various approaches to preparing teachers for licensing exams. For example, in countries such as Singapore, curriculum changes are usually directly linked to improved teacher training programs, which reflect the high licensing exam approval rates. Such educational policies underline a critical aspect: effective implementation of curriculum changes can lead to significant improvements in teachers' readiness and performance (Ignacio, Cristobal, and David, 2022).

Comparatively, in the Philippines, the curriculum for teacher education was subjected to remarkable transformations aimed at improving educational production. The latest reforms emphasize results-based education, which is believed to be better aligned with labor market demands and to improve teachers' levels of competence (Cadasales et al., 2023). However, despite these efforts, some teacher training institutions have adopted such changes while others remain entrenched in outdated practices. Consequently, their graduates may not perform ideally in licensing exams, as highlighted by Amança & Maramag (2020).

Moreover, Philippine data indicate that the performance of the Teacher Licensing Exam (LET) is closely linked to the quality of teacher training programs and the curricula used (GABASA & Rqueño, 2021). A study by Balanquit, Agnes, and Nool (2023) revealed that the educational achievement of faculty members significantly influences students' performance in the LET. Teachers themselves need to be well-versed in the updated curriculum to offer effective guidance to their students. This cyclical relationship highlights the need for continuous professional development among educators and coaches who align with current curriculum structures.

Given these circumstances, this study aims to determine the effect of the curriculum shift from the old curriculum to the new curriculum on the academic performance and Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) results of graduates in both the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) and Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) programs. It further seeks to assess whether differences exist between the two curricula in terms of academic achievement, LET subject-area performance, passing rates, and the relationship between academic performance and LET outcomes. Specifically, it investigates how the overall academic

performance of graduates differs between the two curricula and whether these differences translate into variations in the results of the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). The study further explores graduates' performance in specific LET subject areas, including General Education, Professional Education, and Majorship, and examines the relationship between their overall academic performance and their LET outcomes under both curricula. In addition, it considers the passing rates of graduates in the LET and the implications of these findings for evaluating the effectiveness of curriculum reforms in preparing competent and professionally ready teachers. By addressing these concerns, the study aims to provide insights into how curricular changes influence academic readiness, licensure success, and the overall quality of teacher education programs.

The significance of this study lies in its ability to provide insights into the relationship between curriculum reforms and licensure performance. It will benefit policymakers in crafting more effective education policies, teacher education institutions in strengthening their programs, and future teachers in gaining better preparation for licensure examinations. Additionally, it contributes to the growing body of knowledge on curriculum reform and teacher quality assurance.

This study is anchored in the conceptual framework that curriculum serves as the blueprint of teacher training, directly influencing competence, readiness, and eventual success in licensure examinations. The theoretical grounding emphasizes that effective curriculum reforms, supported by teacher training quality, can create a cyclical improvement in teacher performance. The paradigm of this research illustrates the interconnection between curriculum change (independent variable), licensure exam performance (dependent variable), and institutional implementation as a moderating factor.

The scope of this study is limited to evaluating the link between curriculum reforms and the performance of graduates in the Licensure Examination for Teachers within selected teacher education institutions in the Philippines. It does not extend to other professional licensure examinations or cover teachers already in long-term practice, focusing instead on recent graduates directly affected by the new curriculum.

In conclusion, the implications of curriculum changes in teacher licensing exams are deep and multifaceted. When analyzing Philippine data alongside international trends, a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities presented by these reforms emerges. This research is therefore essential, as it will contribute to the ongoing dialogue around educational quality, teacher training, and the future of licensing exams, while advocating for policies that truly reflect the needs of students and educators in the evolving educational landscape.

Statement of the problem

This study aims to determine the effect of the curriculum shift from the old curriculum to the new curriculum on the academic performance and Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) results of graduates in the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) and Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) programs. Specifically, it seeks to assess whether significant differences exist between the two curricula in terms of overall academic achievement, LET

subject-area performance in General Education, Professional Education, and Majorship, and passing rates of graduates. Furthermore, the study examines the relationship between the academic performance of graduates and their LET outcomes under both curricula, with the end goal of evaluating the effectiveness of curriculum reforms in producing competent and professionally prepared teachers.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design, which was deemed most appropriate since the investigation did not manipulate any variables but instead sought to describe the existing relationship between curriculum changes and the performance of graduates in the Licensure Examination for Teachers. The descriptive aspect was used to present the demographic profile and academic records of the respondents, while the correlational aspect determined the degree of relationship between academic performance, curriculum type, and LET results. This design was suitable because it allowed the researcher to establish whether differences in curriculum exposure, specifically between the old and new curricula, were significantly related to graduates' performance in the licensure examination.

The respondents of this study were graduates of the College of Teacher Education of King's College of the Philippines-Bambang Inc. Specifically, the old curriculum graduates were from the 2018–2019 batch, while the new curriculum respondents were from the 2022–2023 batch. The sampling procedure employed was purposive sampling, as the study specifically targeted graduates who had taken the LET and whose academic records were available. The study initially aimed for total enumeration of all eligible graduates, but due to limitations in accessibility and communication, only 11 graduates from the old curriculum and 11 graduates from the new curriculum were able to provide the necessary data and consent. Despite the smaller size, this group was sufficient to represent both curriculum groups for comparative analysis.

The primary data for the study came from the respondents themselves, who provided their ratings and performance in the Licensure Examination for Teachers. Academic performance data, such as grade point averages during their college years, were obtained from the Office of the Registrar with the respondents' consent. To ensure ethical compliance, the respondents were asked to sign consent forms granting the researcher permission to access their academic records and use their LET results for research purposes.

The study was conducted during the academic year 2024–2025 at King's College of the Philippines–Bambang Inc., located in Bambang, Nueva Vizcaya. The institution was selected as the locale since it offers teacher education programs that have produced graduates under both the old curriculum, particularly the 2018–2019 batch, and the new curriculum, represented by the 2022–2023 batch. The timeframe covered the entire period of data collection, validation, and analysis. The data gathering process followed a series of steps. First, formal letters were prepared and sent to the College of Teacher Education and the Office of the Registrar to seek approval to conduct the study and request access to student records. Upon approval, the researcher identified graduates from both the old and new curricula and attempted to reach them through various communication channels. The graduates were informed of the purpose of the study and were provided with consent forms, which they signed to authorize the retrieval of their academic

records and LET results. Only those who granted consent were included in the study. After collecting the data, the researcher organized the information by grouping graduates according to curriculum type and prepared the dataset for analysis.

The raw data gathered were carefully checked for completeness and accuracy before being encoded for analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to determine the level of academic performance and the LET results of the respondents. To determine the relationship between academic performance and LET performance, inferential statistics were applied. Specifically, the Spearman Rho was used to measure the strength and direction of relationships between variables, while t-tests were employed to compare the performance of old and new curriculum graduates. The statistical analyses were performed at a 0.05 level of significance to ensure the reliability of findings.

The study observed strict ethical procedures to ensure the protection of participants. The respondents were informed about the objectives of the research and were asked to voluntarily participate by signing informed consent forms. They were assured that their academic records and LET results would only be used for research purposes and kept strictly confidential. Access to records was granted only upon the respondents' permission, and the researcher ensured that the data were handled with integrity, transparency, and respect for the privacy of the graduates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Academic performance of respondents

This study involved 22 respondents, composed of 11 graduates from the old curriculum (2018–2019 batch) and 11 graduates from the new curriculum (2022–2023 batch) of the College of Teacher Education at King's College of the Philippines–Bambang Inc. As outlined in the methodology, purposive sampling was used to identify graduates with both complete academic records and Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) results. Academic performance was determined through grade point averages obtained from the Registrar's Office, with informed consent from the respondents.

The academic ratings revealed that graduates from both the old and new curricula generally performed well, consistently falling within the "Above Average" range. For the old curriculum group, the recorded scores included 81.66 (Average), 84.42 (Average), 86.52 (Above Average), 89.14 (Above Average), 87.21 (Above Average), 82.04 (Average), 84.36 (Average), 89.53 (Excellent), 87.82 (Above Average), 86.04 (Above Average), and 80.32 (Average). This resulted in a mean score of 85.36, which corresponds to an "Above Average" qualitative description. Similarly, the new curriculum group showed scores of 89.16 (Above Average), 80.87 (Average), 84.52 (Above Average), 89.21 (Above Average), 87.97 (Above Average), 88.04 (Above Average), 85.59 (Above Average), 88.67 (Above Average), 86.82 (Above Average), 88.51 (Above Average), and 85.16 (Above Average), producing a higher mean of 86.77, also interpreted as "Above Average." Notably, while the old curriculum included one "Excellent" performance, the new curriculum displayed a stronger clustering within the "Above Average" bracket.

These findings indicate that curriculum reforms did not produce radical shifts in overall academic competence but supported stable and commendable levels of achievement. The slightly higher mean score of the new curriculum suggests that curriculum redesign, instructional improvements, and enhanced program alignment may have contributed to improved readiness for professional demands. As observed by Villaflores (2023) and Llego (2024), curriculum updates across disciplines such as teacher education and nursing can foster better confidence and preparedness, though other external factors such as review programs, institutional support, and personal study habits remain essential influences on performance.

Test of significant difference in academic performance

Statistical testing confirmed that the academic performance of both groups was significant. For the old curriculum, the mean score was 85.37, with $t = 91.886$, $p < .001$, and a 95% confidence interval ranging from 83.2985 to 87.4387. For the new curriculum, the mean was 86.77, with $t = 112.697$, $p < .001$, and a 95% confidence interval ranging from 85.0589 to 88.4902. Both results fall well below the 0.05 level of significance, confirming that the observed academic achievements did not occur by chance. Although the new curriculum mean was slightly higher, the small gap between the two groups indicates that both curricula were capable of producing academically prepared graduates.

These outcomes affirm the role of curriculum reforms in ensuring stable educational outcomes, consistent with Chaou et al. (2022), who found that national curriculum changes enhance student preparation, and Campbell-Phillips (2020), who emphasized that reforms generate improved learning experiences. While the differences in academic performance were statistically significant, they suggest incremental rather than radical improvement.

LET performance of graduates

The results of the Licensure Examination for Teachers revealed greater disparities between the two curricula compared to academic performance. For the old curriculum group, scores were 83 (Average), 84.2 (Average), 79.6 (Average), 83 (Average), 83.6 (Average), 80.2 (Average), 85.2 (Above Average), 85.2 (Above Average), 83.8 (Average), 83.6 (Average), and 83.8 (Average), producing a mean score of 80.98, classified as “Average.” By contrast, the new curriculum graduates recorded 75.2 (Below Average), 79.4 (Below Average), 83.8 (Average), 77.6 (Below Average), 71.6 (Failed), 74.6 (Failed), 74.6 (Failed), 80.6 (Average), 77.2 (Below Average), 74.4 (Failed), and 79.4 (Below Average), resulting in a lower mean of 78.48, interpreted as “Below Average.”

The comparison shows that old curriculum graduates achieved stronger LET performance, not only in terms of higher mean scores but also in consistency. Most of their results fell within the “Average” and “Above Average” categories, whereas the new curriculum group exhibited more variability, with several results categorized as “Below Average” or “Failed.” These findings suggest that while the new curriculum introduced innovations, its implementation may still be in a transitional phase, with uneven effectiveness across institutions and graduates. Gabasa and Rqueño (2021) and Llego (2024) argue that curriculum reforms require continuous refinement and full integration before yielding consistent licensure outcomes.

Test of significant difference in LET performance

A test of significant difference further confirmed this disparity. The old curriculum recorded a mean LET score of 81.76 with $t = 77.541$ and $p < .001$, while the new curriculum had a mean score of 78.56 with $t = 61.776$ and $p < .001$. Both values were significant, but the higher mean of the old curriculum suggests a slight competitive advantage. This resonates with Ow-Yeong, Yeter, and Ali (2023), who observed that curriculum maturity and stability often correlate with stronger licensure performance. Nonetheless, studies by Abao et al. (2023) and Amança and Maramag (2020) emphasize that both curricular approaches still provide a solid foundation for preparing beginning teachers, although the newer system requires adjustments to match the effectiveness of its predecessor.

LET subject-area performance

A closer examination of specific subject areas—General Education, Professional Education, and Majorship—revealed further insights. For Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) graduates under the old curriculum, the mean scores were 79.44 in General Education, 80.89 in Professional Education, and 75.00 in Majorship. In contrast, BSED graduates under the new curriculum achieved higher means of 83.56 in General Education, 85.00 in Professional Education, and 79.44 in Majorship. This suggests that while the old curriculum group struggled more in their specialization, the new curriculum offered improvements across all three areas.

For Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) graduates, the old curriculum produced mean scores of 83.00 in General Education, 80.50 in Professional Education, and 78.00 in Majorship. New curriculum BEED graduates recorded slightly higher averages of 81.00 in General Education, 82.30 in Professional Education, and 78.00 in Majorship. These results demonstrate that curriculum reform positively influenced performance in specific LET subject areas, particularly in General and Professional Education. This aligns with the findings of Rosa and Vargas (2021), who highlighted the value of reforms in strengthening subject-area competencies, and Amança and Maramag (2020), who confirmed that updated programs support improved licensure performance.

Relationship between academic performance and LET performance

The relationship between academic performance and LET results was tested using both Spearman's rho and Pearson's r. For the old curriculum graduates, Spearman's rho was 0.516 and Pearson's r was 0.751, while for the new curriculum graduates, Spearman's rho was 0.862 and Pearson's r was 0.505. All values exceeded the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that there was no statistically significant relationship between academic grades and LET performance. This means that higher academic ratings did not necessarily predict better LET outcomes, and conversely, average performers in college could still achieve strong licensure results. This echoes the conclusions of Casian, Mugo, and Claire (2021), who emphasized that

review programs, test-taking strategies, and external conditions also play key roles in licensure success.

Passing rates of LET takers

The passing rates of LET takers revealed important contrasts. Under the old curriculum, 6 out of 9 BEED graduates passed, yielding a 66.67% passing rate, while 46 out of 70 BSED graduates passed, corresponding to a 65.71% rate. In the new curriculum, however, BEED graduates achieved a perfect 100% passing rate, as all 6 candidates passed, while only 9 out of 28 BSED graduates passed, corresponding to a much lower 32.14% passing rate. These results highlight a striking discrepancy: the new curriculum appears highly effective for BEED graduates but less so for BSED graduates, raising questions about program implementation and consistency.

Scholars such as Villaflores (2023) and Barinario et al. (2023) stress that curriculum alignment with licensure requirements and updated pedagogical approaches can significantly influence performance. While the new curriculum shows promise in producing strong BEED outcomes, the low BSED passing rate signals areas that require further refinement. Olvida et al. (2024) and Ghamrawi et al. (2023) argue that continuous curriculum evaluation is essential to ensure that reforms equip all graduates with the skills and confidence necessary for licensure success.

Synthesis of findings

In sum, the results highlight a complex picture. Both curricula produced graduates with commendable academic performance, with the new curriculum showing slightly higher mean academic ratings. However, the old curriculum group outperformed the new curriculum in overall LET results, demonstrating more consistency and fewer failures. In terms of subject areas, the new curriculum showed improvements in General and Professional Education, while Majorship scores still revealed gaps. Passing rate analysis further emphasized that while the new curriculum supported strong outcomes for BEED graduates, it fell short for BSED graduates. Importantly, no significant correlation was found between academic grades and LET performance, suggesting that additional factors such as exam preparation, study habits, and institutional support remain critical determinants of licensure success.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study revealed that graduates under both the old and new curricula demonstrated consistently commendable levels of academic achievement, with mean ratings that generally fell within the “Above Average” category. While both curricular frameworks effectively prepared students for their undergraduate programs, the new curriculum showed a modest but notable improvement in overall academic performance compared to the old curriculum. This slight advantage may be attributed to results-based reforms and program enhancements introduced in the revised curriculum, which strengthened learning outcomes and sustained student preparedness throughout their academic journey.

In terms of licensure examination results, the new curriculum graduates performed better than their counterparts in specific subject areas, particularly in General Education and Professional Education, suggesting that reforms in curriculum design had a positive effect on subject-specific competencies. However, performance in Majorship subjects remained inconsistent, with results indicating a need for closer alignment between specialization content and the competencies assessed in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). Moreover, despite improved academic performance and subject-area outcomes under the new curriculum, the overall LET performance of graduates did not consistently reflect these advantages. The old curriculum group outperformed the new curriculum in terms of mean LET scores, achieving an “Average” classification, while the new curriculum produced a lower mean categorized as “Below Average.” This inconsistency underscores that academic success in college does not directly translate to licensure performance.

Statistical analysis confirmed this observation, as no significant relationship was found between students’ overall academic performance and their LET results. Students who achieved higher academic ratings during their college years did not necessarily perform better in the licensure examination, while others with average academic ratings were still able to pass or even excel. This finding suggests that external factors, such as access to review programs, study habits, exam readiness, and even personal conditions during testing, exert a significant influence on LET outcomes. Passing rates further demonstrated the variability in results, with the new curriculum producing a perfect 100% passing rate for Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) graduates, while Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) graduates under the same curriculum showed a much lower passing rate of only 32.14%. By comparison, old curriculum graduates achieved passing rates of 66.67% for BEED and 65.71% for BSED, indicating more consistent though not exceptional outcomes across programs. These findings highlight that curriculum reform alone does not guarantee higher licensure success, but it contributes meaningfully to improved academic preparation and subject-specific competence.

In light of these results, several recommendations are advanced to strengthen the curriculum and ensure more consistent outcomes in both academic and licensure performance. The College of Teacher Education (CTE) may consider conducting a thorough review and refinement of the new curriculum, with particular emphasis on Majorship subjects, to ensure that both content and pedagogy are effectively aligned with LET standards. Establishing a structured feedback mechanism that allows students to share their experiences and suggestions regarding the curriculum could provide valuable insights for continuous improvement. Furthermore, exploring the internal and external factors influencing LET success—such as study habits, mental health, and access to resources—could help identify areas for targeted interventions to address existing gaps in student preparation.

Mentorship programs connecting current students with alumni who have excelled in the LET may also be beneficial, as such initiatives can foster the exchange of effective study strategies, exam techniques, and practical insights. Additionally, offering professional development opportunities for faculty members is crucial, particularly in strengthening instructional strategies in challenging subject areas such as Majorship and Professional Education. Organizing seminars, workshops, and review sessions earlier in the academic cycle, while dedicating greater focus on specialization areas, could provide students with more robust

preparation. Inviting recognized LET review experts to deliver lectures or workshops may further enrich the preparation process and inspire confidence among test takers. This recommendation aligns with the findings of Colicol, Puig, and Judan (2022), whose evaluation of a transformative review program demonstrated significant improvements in LET performance when intensive review mechanisms were institutionalized.

Finally, implementing regular assessments and semester-based feedback loops would allow CTE to closely monitor student progress and provide timely support where necessary. The integration of these measures will not only ensure that curriculum reforms achieve their intended impact but will also contribute to a more supportive and responsive teacher education environment. By addressing both curricular content and external influences on licensure performance, institutions can better prepare graduates for the demands of professional teaching, thereby fulfilling their role in producing competent, confident, and effective educators for the nation's schools.

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